

An Empirical Study on Marketing of Educational Services by Business Schools in Bangalore to Post-Millennial

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Mr. Prithwiraj Das

Research Scholar, Shyam University, Jaipur

Ms. N. Haritha

MBA Student, Bangalore University

Abstract

Over the period of time, ways to seek information's on best possible management courses has also evolved and plays an essential role in the minds of the Post-Millennials. Especially when the horizon of dreams & a sense of urgency are on a rise among them. Post millennials are confident, ambitious, smartest and focussed youth of our country born between 1997 – till present day. They seek information's for the best of education & courses to excel in competitive world. There are many educational institutions across Bangalore city providing opportunities to millennials & post millennials to help them select the best course for their successful career. In these circumstances educational institutions must make Post- Millennials aware on best educational scopes on offer. Here comes a situation where gravity of admission marketing strategies plays an indispensable role. An effort made in this empirical paper is to find out the impact of marketing of educational services to the Post-Millennials. The study adopts various qualitative & quantitative methods in analyzing the primary and secondary data collected for the study. The Research presented in this paper reveals interesting findings on factors determining student's decision on selecting management courses, placements in the institutions. In the given competitive environment in education sector, a focussed, strategic & impactful efforts towards education marketing through various methods are being tried by various educational institutes.

This paper would establish the impact factors of various education marketing strategies on Post-Millennial strategized by business schools enabling them to select among the best management programs offered in Bangalore.

Keywords: Education , Marketing Strategy , B-School , Post-Millennial student, Impact

Introduction

Competition is everywhere throughout the world Especially Education service as it is dynamic sector. Today's education system change the entire system of learning by developing a new revolution. Nowadays, most of the education institutions especially, B-schools university, have recognized the important of those tools and have extensively implemented marketing strategies on operation in order to increase the student enrolment.

Marketing of education is moreover gaining power with the entry of private institutions, change in people's attitude, preferences towards education and the changing scope for the different courses being offered. The technological changes and different global boundaries have increased the importance of marketing for education services. The education service can be described as a high contact, consumer and people based service (Gibbs and Maringe, 2008). However, the main issue of strategic marketing accomplishment is to adapt the marketing tools has to be consistent related to the student desire. Understanding the millennials decision making is consequential for institutional administrator in the circumstances of competition. Previous studies found that marketing factors influencing student decision (Ming, 2010; Dao and Thorpe, 2015; Lau, 2016; Sakkamonvaree, 2011; Promwong, 2012). This confirmed that marketing factors should be recognized.

The task of the education institution at business school is to create conditions under which educators implement their intellectual and creative potential, forming and leading a pathway of professional mobility. According to some study, educational institutions are product oriented rather than market or student oriented. They realize themselves as producers of certain educational programs, rather than as satisfiers of certain learning needs. This lack of marketing orientation, keeps those managing educational institutions from realizing and exploiting the role that promotion could play in attaining their organizational objectives.

Literature Review

Nataliya Kalenskaya, Ilshat Gafurov, Aida Novenkova, International Conference on Applied Economics (ICOAE) 2013, Article Procedia Economics and Finance 5 • December 2013 with 1,139 Reads DOI: 10.1016/S2212-5671(13)00044-0 Marketing of Educational Services: Research on Service Providers Satisfaction --Modern circumstances require educational systems to be more flexible, able to adapt changes quickly. Now university professors must not only transfer knowledge to learners, but to be their advisor to the universe knowledge, help them to understand the significance of learning and personal responsibility for the results of their studies. Therefore marketing is necessary to build a systematic approach to solving of problem according to the criteria of modern education system and several requirements for the quality of education for all segments of consumers. marketing may achieve something more if it considers student desires as a peak priority.

Michaela Purcaru, Natalia Manea: THE EVOLUTION OF EDUCATIONAL MARKETING, Article December 2017 with 4,337 Reads DOI: 10.26458/1744-Education marketing is focuses on people, demands, their needs, aspirations, lifestyles and freedom of choice. In this article authors also discussed about the social marketing which applies the techniques and principles of marketing to generate communication and delivery value, in order to determine the audience target behaviour for the benefit of society.

Creating Marketing Strategies For Higher Education Institutions, Professor Lidia Białoń Warsaw Management University, Poland DOI: 10.14611/minib.18.04.2015 Creating Marketing Strategies For Higher Education Institutions, Professor Lidia.13- Author Discussed about the definition of marketing, According to p.kotler, marketing is a Social Process and management thanks to which particular buyers get what they need and want to achieve by offering, creating and exchange of goods and services providing value. Applying p.kotler's definition to universities, the buyers of educational service are high school graduates ,might be Illiterates their parents. Also employers can be included in this group. These buyers(parents) generate demand for educational services. marketing strategy will require major modifications as they expect acquisition of Skills, reliable knowledge and which they will be able to use in their future professional careers.

Objectives

1. To study the impact factors of education marketing strategies on students.
2. To estimate the reach of most popular education marketing strategy in Bangalore.
3. To ascertain the most popular education marketing medium helping millennial in short listing their courses.

Significance of the Study

This study would help to analyse different management education admission strategise and the convenience along with high impact factors on millennials to choose their courses in different colleges.

Research Methodology

Education service is one of the fastest developing sector around the world which generating large scale employment and revenue. There have been major amendment occurred in recent education technology driven by foreign education on the stipulation. With the effect of globalization, the call for better education has increased, largely through private participation across the nations. E-education market is flourishing segment with high growth potential in the industry. In 2007-08, US inaugurated 60% of the global market and Europe constituted for 15% market. In spite of the decline in the economy the number of students going to abroad for studies increasing globally. The global education sector has experienced growth at a great rate supported by the recognised developing countries (especially India & China).

Australia has developed an efficient and effective higher education system. Almost one million students have enrolled in higher education in 2007, with an hike of almost 4.7% from the level in 2006. In Japan continuing education programs are most on demand due to rapid aggravated conditions of growing population and provide opportunities for U.S. extension universities an colleges. Indonesia is considered as one of the major markets for US educational institutes. In Korea there is increased demand in the private education market at the secondary and even primary education level. English is a very popular language for Belgian citizens, due to its rising demand in children and adult group. In India, private sector has a strong hold in education industry beginning from pre-schools to universities. The markets which contribute to the global education sector include Ireland, EU and Asia-Pacific and also countries. The report also highlights the emerging market which has a greater potential to develop the education industry. The article also discusses the contribution of upgraded technology and recent trends in the market. The report has also covered future prediction of education industry in different parts of the world.

The second largest industry is the global education industry after healthcare. It had a market of US\$~ trillion in 2009 grew from US\$~ trillion in 2007.

- In 2009, tuition revenue in Ireland reached to US\$~ million, an increase of almost US\$~ million from 2006/7, driven by increased number of students in this period.
- 6.1 million students graduated in China in 2009. Almost 68% of the students got employed till 1st of July. In comparison to the statistics in 2008, there were 520,000 less students, but still 68% of the students got employed.
- Indonesia is considered as one of the major markets for US educational institutes.
- In 2008, the size of South Korea's private education market is estimated to have grown to 30 trillion won (US\$~ billion) from US\$~ billion in 2007, with the English learning industry taking up nearly half of the market share.

This empirical study is undertaken to study the impact of marketing of education services enabling institutions to understand the factors helping millennial in selecting institutions. The study was

conducted on the basis of primary data collected through survey method. Samples were collected from the students who are studying in their first & final years of post graduation. The questionnaire was prepared & circulated among the students through Google Forms, where the online survey questions were uploaded by the authors. The questionnaire web link was sent to the respondents. The method used here is convenience sampling method. It is the best Sampling Technique to be used for this paper. Sample size was 80.

1. Does B-School education marketing strategies help students to actually find their desired courses & institutions?

As the survey provides us the detailed study about the marketing strategy, where greater proportion of the students believes that marketing of education services helped them to find their desired college. In the above diagram it represents 54 percentage of the students are strongly agreed.

In detail, out of 80 students 43 were agreed, 7 students are strongly agreed, 24 of them are neutral, 4 students are disagreed and 1 student strongly disagreed.

2. Does the marketing approaches adopted by B-Schools really helps students in their selection/decision making process?

From the above pie chart we can say that marketing of education service would affect the enrolment of students in the B-Schools. In this scenario also students have agreed in a greater percentage that the students of B-School are affected on enrolment process. The above pie indicates that 61 percentages of the students have agreed.

In detailed out of 80 responses collected 16 percentages of the students have strongly agreed 4 percentages of students have strongly disagreed 5 percentage of students have disagreed and 14 percentage of the students had been neutral in their answers.

3. Are the information provided by B-schools during their admission/marketing time adequate & reliable for the students and their parents?

In the above case that the information provided by the B-Schools varies, not in a greater proportion but slight changes in then in the above diagram presented it show that 35 percentage of the students have remained neutral in their answers.

As the survey conducted provides that out of 80 responses 31 percentage of the students have agreed that the information provided is not sufficient to then and 13 percentage of the students have strongly agreed 21 percentage of the students have disagreed that the information provided is not sufficient to them.

4. Do you feel without education marketing approaches, it will be difficult for student community to actually decide & enrol for their choice of course & institution?

In the above situation marketing of education services have been helpful to the students to select the best B-Schools across Bangalore. In the above pie it shows that 39 percentage of the students have agreed that the marketing have helped them to find their best B-School across Bangalore.

In the above pie diagram students have their different opinion where as 22 percentage of the students have strongly agreed 4 percentage have strongly disagreed 8 percentage have disagreed and 27 percentage of the students have been neutral in their answers.

5. Do you ever feel education as an investment and outcome of your education is as return on that investment?

In the above pie chart it shows that students are receiving the level of investment done in their courses not at a greater proportion but in a considerable proportion where 45 percentage of the students believe that the investment done by them has been served by their institutions where as 4 percentage of students strongly agreed, 20 percentage of the students are disagreed and 31 percentage of the students remained neutral.

6. Do you decide your educational choices by your own?

In the below representation students were able to take their educational decisions on their own at a very increasing ratio.

In detail 66 students are considering themselves as decision makers of their education where as rest of the students are dependent on others.

7. From where do usually search for information regarding course of your interests.

In the above diagram we can consider that the substantial amount of the students have been able to gather information about their courses through internet. Showing attentions to the details provided by the survey conducted that 64 of the students were able to secure information through the help of technology, considerably internet that would be the maximum percentage level. Where as 4 students were able to collect through the means of newspaper, 3 students from the banners displayed and 1 student from the big hoardings.

8. Approximately how long you decide to study at certain university or college.

As we see in the above result survey chart the period taken to select a certain university by the students across Bangalore are ranging. 38 of the students were able to decide during the last year 24 of the students after they were offered the place and 18 of the students decided their university more than one year ago.

9. How did you searched for information about your current institution where you are studying now?

As the above pie chart shows us the detailed information about the students reference to their university by selective community of the people. Majority of the students were able to find their university by their friends. 31 students by their friends, 21 students by their own, 16 students by their parents, 8 students by the college admission department and 3 of the students by media.

10. What are the parameters you look for in education marketing to shortlist institutions?

On certain criteria students select their universities, in the below illustrated diagram students can be provided with the assistance of the above aspects. 50 percentage of the students that is 40 of the students consider all the above given option, 16 f the students on the basis of the education provided by the universities, 13 students on the bases of the placements, 6 students selected none if the above, 4 students by looking at the infrastructure and remaining students on the basis of the reputation.

Findings & Conclusion

1. Students are open to varied approaches in marketing of education by B-Schools as it helps them to gain right information & momentum towards their career choice.
2. Students do rely significantly on the information collected through various mediums of marketing done by institutions.
3. Various methods of marketing of education eventually helps students with multiple information which further helps to establish clarity on their career choice.
4. A large section of students have started evaluating institute & course as an investment & hence they seek information which proves good return on the same investment.
5. Friends play an important source to receive reference & suggestions on different courses & institutions.
6. Students do have set parameters for evaluating a particular course and an institution.
7. There is a significant dependency on internet & related sources for initial enquiry and interest.
8. The decision making on course & institute remains primarily with the particular student.

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